

OUR SOUND SPACE (OSS) – AN INSTALLATION FOR PARTICIPATORY AND INTERACTIVE EXPLORATION OF SOUNDSCAPES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of an interactive tool which allows playing different soundscapes by mixing diverse environmental sounds on demand. This tool is titled Our Sound Space (OSS) and has been developed as part of an ongoing project where we test methods and tools for the participation of young people in spatial planning. As such OSS is meant to offer new opportunities to engage youth in talks about planning, placemaking and more sustainable living environments. In this paper, we describe an implementation of OSS that we are using as an interactive soundscape installation sited in a public place daily visited by people from a diversity of entities (e.g. university, a gymnasium, a restaurant, start-ups). The OSS installation is designed to allow simultaneous activation of several pre-recorded sounds broadcast through four loudspeakers. The installation is interactive, meaning that it can be activated and operated by anyone via smartphones and is designed to allow interaction among multiple people at the same time and space.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ambient sounds impact greatly the way people perceive the surrounding environment. In an urban setting, ambient sound induces thoughts and emotions, influencing the way we feel and behave. This consequently impacts our perception of safety and security and how we feel about the places where we live, work, study and socialize. Acoustic environment as perceived or experienced by people, also known as soundscape [1], is an important factor shaping the quality of life in urban environments and as such there has been great interest in it over the years. Most of that scholarship has centred on unwanted ambient sound i.e. noise documenting the negative implications noise has on human health [2, 3]. Due to the weight of the matter well-structured legal frameworks, guidelines and tools have been set in place to guide spatial planning on the task of reducing, limiting, and preventing the negative effects noise can have for people [4].

On the other hand, recent research has begun to seriously study and explore the positive effects that other types of ambient sounds can have on people and there is a growing

interest to study urban soundscapes which have the potential to offer a restorative, regenerative and calming experience [3, 5]. This research presents a novel opportunity to initiate a conversation about the quality of life in urban environments. It has the potential to raise new questions about both the mental and physical well-being of city residents. Also, by bringing forward a more direct conceptual (and practical) connection between human senses with our mental and physical health in cities new opportunities are generated for the inclusion of less represented groups, or groups that traditionally are not central in planning. Recent research is already exploring the potential to work with soundscapes in a planning context for the engagement of children, young people and differently-able adults [6, 7]. With the research reported in this paper, we seek to contribute to this debate and report on an activity centered on the development of a new tool meant to create new opportunities to bring soundscapes in participatory planning processes with young people. The tool Our Sound Space (OSS) operates via mobile technology and allows the use of different soundscapes. Participatory planning processes most often rely on spoken words, maps, or images. These fit some youth but might not fit well all. OSS allows us to bring urban sonic environments into participatory processes and as such it offers opportunities to engage youth in conversations about the places they live and how they would develop them. In the following sections, we first position our work on soundscapes as interdisciplinary and locate it in the context of spatial planning, then we continue with a description of the OSS tool and its use in placemaking. We then conclude the paper with some reflections.

2. USE AND POTENTIAL OF SOUNDSCAPES IN PARTICIPATORY PLANNING WITH YOUNG PEOPLE

Over the past 25 years, cities around the world have experienced significant growth, and this trend is set to continue at a rapid pace in Europe, where urbanization is expected to increase by 83.7% by 2050 [8]. This growth is attributed to various factors, including population expansion and densification, which have raised critical questions regarding the direction and governance of urban development. Historically, the prevailing trend has been that few people have had a say in urban planning decisions, resulting in the construction of infrastructure such as roads, housing, and malls, without adequate consideration of community needs and participation. However, scientific research has been documenting how the negative effects of fast-growing ur-

Figure 1. Our Sound Space is a tool for investigating the intersection of three research areas: “Children and Youth Geographies”, “Multi-modal Interaction”, and “Sustainable Spatial Planning”.

banization, such as air and noise pollution, impact the mental and physical health of residents, and the need to plan for more sustainable living environments is gaining traction across policy and practice [2, 3]. This has resulted in an increased interest in questions about equity and well-being in cities, and the subsequent opening of participatory processes to less represented groups [4]. For instance, in Sweden, there is in place a formal requirement to also include children and young people in planning processes [9].

However, including younger demographic groups or other underrepresented groups in planning may present challenges for planners who are accustomed to well-structured and organized participatory processes centered on data, expert knowledge, and legal requirements. These traditional methods may not be suitable for children and young people, who have different perspectives and ways of operating than adult experts, and may not find them useful [10–12]. As such, planners must be willing to adapt their processes to accommodate the needs and preferences of diverse groups, including considering alternative approaches to engagement and decision-making such as creative methods allowing for the diversity of expressiveness that characterizes younger demographic groups [13, 14]. Literature has reported on processes where easy-to-use and access methods as is for instance paper and pencil, crafting and coloring, have been used [10].

The research reported here contributes to this trend with the description and discussion of a novel tool which operates at the level of soundscapes. The tool is named Our Sound Space, and its core premise is that it allows working with different sounds of places, providing a novel and user-friendly approach to incorporating soundscapes of places and living environments into participatory processes. Exploring how different soundscapes affect safety and security perceptions can help us better understand how the built

environment and other urban elements impact safety, and how this may affect access to urban infrastructure and nature. Additionally, soundscapes can offer valuable insights into the restorative potential of natural areas like parks, wetlands, urban forests, and recreational tracks. This has become an important focus for planners seeking to improve public health through increased urban nature access [15].

Integrating soundscapes into participatory activities can provide valuable insights, when young people and children need to be involved. By enabling them to access the sounds of their environment, they can better understand how planning interventions could impact their surroundings, including changes to the sonic environment such as increased traffic noise, sounds of nature or human activities. This additional layer of information can help them reflect on how they perceive such changes and provide feedback on specific planning-related questions posed by professionals such as planners, practitioners, and city-makers. Moreover, using soundscapes in participatory processes can help to further understand the needs, values, and preferences of citizens and residents (see Figure 1).

3. OUR SOUND SPACE: STEPS TAKEN

We started our work on soundscape with an explorative workshop held in December 2021 with a group of stakeholders/representatives from public and private organizations active in Flemingsberg (Huddinge), followed up by additional research on soundscapes and planning, which eventually led us to the development of OSS - Our Sound Space tool.

To mark the completion of OSS in Dec 2022, in collaboration with Hemsö¹ (a company owning several commercial buildings in Flemingsberg), we created a public installation for a period of 7 months (December 2022 - June 2023). The ambition behind using OSS as a public installation is to make it widely accessible and test it as a place-making tool. We continue exploring questions located at the intersection of smart city design, planning and human-computer interaction with special attention to the positioning of less represented groups in that context.

3.1 Design of the OSS app

At the beginning of the development process, a first version of OSS was designed so that users could continuously explore on their mobile device a set of sounds in a two-dimensional space. The system produced one sound at a time, automatically established by calculating the average of all positions chosen on the 2D interface by all users visiting the installation at the same time. In September 2022 we organized a test with a group of ten people. Results showed issues with usability: the more visitors were present, the less effective the individual’s action was on the overall soundscape. That type of sound control was intended to stimulate the direct collaboration between users, including verbal communication, necessary to control which sound to activate collectively. However, this expectation was not met.

¹ Hemsö www.hemso.se

Figure 2. This is the interface of OSS app, consisting of coloured and numbered buttons. Each number represents a specific sound (see Figure 3 for the detailed list of sounds). Each color represents a different category of sounds: Yellow - human and living, Red - human and not living being, Green - not human and living being, and Blue - not human and not living being. When the color of a button is lighter, it means it has been pressed and the corresponding sound is active.

Taking into account the outcomes of this first test, through progressive refinements in the next design iteration, the current version of OSS app was implemented.

OSS allows selecting among 36 sound files reproducing different sonic environments (soundscapes) (see Figure 3). The files were obtained by editing and mixing several environmental audio recordings². Each sound can be activated and deactivated by each user by means of a control interface. This consists of 36 colored numbered buttons, organized according to a squared grid (see Figure 2), and easily accessible from any browser on a mobile device (see Figure 4).

The 36 sounds are organized on the interface using the following opposite category pairs:

- Human sounds – Non-human sounds
- Sounds generated by living beings – Sounds generated by non-living things

Thus generating four groups of sounds identified on the interface through buttons of four different colors:

- Yellow color: sounds produced by the human body and its activities (e.g. heartbeat, footstep sounds on various surfaces, crowd noises, laughter, applause)

² Here you can find the list of sounds and credits from freesound.org

01 Noisy Crowd	04 Rainforest
02 Children	05 Ants eating
03 Laughter from the audience	06 Cricket
07 Heartbeat	10 Barking dogs
08 Footsteps in mud	11 Frogs
09 Audience clapping	12 Cicadas
13 Footsteps on cobblestone	16 Sheep grazing
14 Footsteps on dry leaves	17 Buzzing of bees
15 Street music	18 Cowbells
19 Urban traffic	22 Iceberg
20 Ship sirens	23 Stream
21 Old printer	24 Wind
25 Train	28 Waves in the harbor
26 Bicycle bell	29 Breaking sea waves
27 Ticking of a city traffic light	30 Light rain
31 Church bells	34 Thunder rumble
32 Overhead planes	35 Rain
33 Factory noises	36 Brook

Figure 3. List of sounds used in OSS: numbers and colors in the table correspond to those of the interface shown in Figure 2.

Figure 4. User interacting with OSS.

- Red color: sounds generated by man-made machines (e.g. different transportation sounds, sounds produced by industrial activities)
- Green color: sounds of non-human living beings (animal sounds)
- Blue color: sounds of non-human and non-living elements (natural elements such as wind, sea, rain, thunder, creaking of an iceberg)

Each button on the interface is associated with a specific type of environmental sound (see Figure 3 for the complete list of sounds). Various soundscapes can be generated by selecting several sounds simultaneously and in different combinations. A maximum limit has been set for the number of sounds that can be simultaneously selected and played to ensure that they can always be perceptually distinguished. This limit has been set to eight sounds af-

Figure 5. The public space where the installation is located

ter several empirical listening tests. The control grid is the same for all users and provides visual feedback on what sounds are being played. When any of the connected users activate a button, its color becomes lighter, and it reverts to its original color when it is deactivated. This also happens on the interface of the other connected users, giving everyone real-time feedback on which sounds are being played by the system loudspeakers.

3.2 OSS set in place as public installation in Flemingsberg Campus

To mark the completion of the development and design phase, we agreed with Hemsö to set up a public installation based on the OSS tool. The installation is sited in the foyer area of NEO, a modern multi-purpose building where many public and private entities have their premises, including the Karolinska Institutet, a restaurant, a coffee shop, and the Widerströmska gymnasium. The foyer is a large and not crowded public space (see Figure 5), and its dimensions are approximately 10 by 10 meters.

The hardware of the installation includes a desktop computer, a sound card, 4 loudspeakers, and a Wi-Fi router. The four loudspeakers have been hung on the ceiling at the four corners of the foyer. The sounds are stereophonic, and every time a sound is reactivated, its two channels are randomly assigned to two of the four loudspeakers to give spatial variety to the listening.

The computer is located in a secured area and functions as a server of a local Wi-Fi network for the whole duration of the installation through a Wi-Fi router. The server, programmed in `node/javascript`, manages the transmission of control data from smartphones to the server and feedback data from the server to the clients. The sound display is handled by software developed in the MaxMSP environment by processing user choices.

Thus, on 8th December 2022, we launched the OSS installation (called with the same name as the app): a long-

term installation lasting until mid-June 2023 (therefore active during the 2023 Sound and Music Computing Conference). Instructions on how to operate OSS are displayed on a roll-up banner and on a sticker on the floor, including an explanation on how to connect a smartphone or tablet to the dedicated local Wi-Fi network and use a QR code to access the interface page (see Figure 6).

3.3 Preliminary evaluation and observations

In this section, we report some preliminary qualitative data collected mostly by site observations over the first one and half months inclusive of feedback received on the opening day when about twenty people were present.

A young person reported that a particular combination of sounds reminded them of summer (even though it was December), and it gave them pleasant sensations and positive emotions. The role of emotions in placemaking is known [10, 16] and the potential of a sonic tool such as OSS in eliciting them is the aspect we are most interested in.

Another visitor of the installation noticed that after a few minutes of inactivity, where no one interacts with the installation anymore, the eventual playing sounds automatically turn off. This was designed so as not to disturb those who have to stay nearby for work, or other reasons, as having a persistent sound over time might hinder concentration and be a disturbance. However, this person suggested always keeping at least one sound active in order to attract passers-by and also because it would be worth exploiting the characterization sound gives to the installation space. In our opinion, a good strategy could be, for the future, using optical sensors to modulate the sound response based on the movement of passers-by for involving and encouraging them to interact with the installation. Another suggestion was to take advantage of the movement data provided by the inertial sensors of smartphones to modulate the sounds, making the interaction more embodied. Fi-

Figure 6. A participant using the QR code on a sticker on the floor to upload OSS on his smartphone. One of the four loudspeakers hanging from the ceiling is highlighted by a white circle.

nally, observing a couple of young people interacting with the installation, we noticed that they were using the installation in a “musical” way: some suitable combinations of sounds were being sought for rhythmic/percussive patterns and interesting combinations that could seem melodic and harmonious. It could be very interesting to think about a future version of OSS designed to facilitate the creation of interactive “musical” experiences using just soundscapes as starting compositional material.

More results and observations will be collected in the following period, also by means of workshops and questionnaires, and will be presented at the SMC conference in June 2023.

3.4 Next steps

We will continue to study the potential of using soundscape in participatory processes with young people. Specifically, we plan to run activities meant to test several aspects including i) the OSS usability, ii) the usefulness to integrate sonic environments into participatory processes, iii) ways in which soundscapes nurture the discussion in planning challenges. We will ask participants to work in small groups and perform tasks or challenges using OSS as a tool to complete their assigned tasks. We will then administer an exit survey with questions on aspects of our interest. We will also collect observational data and look at the outcomes of their work. The different data collected will be

used in triangulation to answer questions about usability, usefulness, and meaningfulness. This work is not yet done but is planned for the coming months.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have introduced Our Sound Space (OSS), a new tool meant to assist participatory spatial planning processes by opening up discussions through interaction with soundscapes. A version of OSS has been employed to set in place an interactive and participatory public installation running from December 2022 to June 2023. Although it is still early to draw any definitive conclusions, preliminary observations and feedback from the first users are promising. However, more work is needed and we plan to continue in the near future with data collection through observation, workshops and questionnaires, to further advance our research and the development of this tool.

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5. REFERENCES

- [1] I. O. for Standardization, “Iso 12913-1: 2014 acoustics—soundscape—part 1: definition and conceptual framework,” *ISO, Geneva*, 2014.
- [2] B. D. Coensel, S. Vanwetswinkel, and D. Botteldooren, “Effects of natural sounds on the perception of road traffic noise,” *The journal of the acoustical society of America*, vol. 129, no. 4, pp. EL148–EL153, 2011.
- [3] M. Hedblom, I. Knez, and B. Gunnarsson, “Bird diversity improves the well-being of city residents,” *Ecology and conservation of birds in urban environments*, pp. 287–306, 2017.
- [4] H. Pineo, *Healthy Urbanism: Designing and Planning Equitable, Sustainable and Inclusive Places*. Springer Nature, 2022.
- [5] K. N. Irvine, P. Devine-Wright, S. R. Payne, R. A. Fuller, B. Painter, and K. J. Gaston, “Green space, soundscape and urban sustainability: an interdisciplinary, empirical study,” *Local Environment*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 155–172, 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549830802522061>
- [6] A. Radicchi, P. Cevikayak Yelmi, A. Chung, P. Jordan, S. Stewart, A. Tsaligopoulos, L. McCunn, and M. Grant, “Sound and the healthy city,” *Cities & Health*, vol. 5, no. 1-2, pp. 1–13, 2021.
- [7] A. Radicchi, “Soundwalking with children for a quieter and healthier city,” *Cities & Health*, vol. 3, no. 1-2, pp. 78–84, 2019.
- [8] *World cities report 2022: Envisaging the future of cities*, 2022.
- [9] R. Rodela and E. Norss, “Opening up spatial planning to the participation of children and youth: the swedish experience,” *European Planning Studies*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 252–269, 2023.
- [10] V. Derr, L. Chawla, and M. Mintzer, *Placemaking with children and youth: Participatory practices for planning sustainable communities*. New Village Press, 2018.
- [11] M. Nordström and M. Wales, “Enhancing urban transformative capacity through children’s participation in planning,” *Ambio*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 507–514, 2019.
- [12] Y. C. Severcan, “Planning for the unexpected: Barriers to young people’s participation in planning in disadvantaged communities,” *International Planning Studies*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 251–269, 2015.
- [13] Ö. Ataol, S. Krishnamurthy, and P. Van Wesemael, “Children’s participation in urban planning and design: A systematic review,” *Children, youth and environments*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 27–47, 2019.
- [14] H. Lauwers and W. Vanderstede, “Spatial planning and opportunities for children’s participation: A local governance network analysis,” *Children Youth and Environments*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 278–289, 2005.
- [15] M. Giusti and K. Samuelsson, “The regenerative compatibility: A synergy between healthy ecosystems, environmental attitudes, and restorative experiences,” *PloS one*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. e0227311, 2020.
- [16] D. Thomas, *Placemaking: An urban design methodology*. Routledge, 2016.